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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the “*Programmable phase plates for electrons*” *Interdisciplinary Training Webinar* - the third in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

The present document is comprised of 4 Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the third Interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT.

The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose this platform it provides the best value for money and offers the added advantage of being very widespread. Users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subject areas: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and explain back the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach for cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant for everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific colloquia, talks, and articles and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the third of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT THIRD INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR:

PROGRAMMABLE PHASE PLATES FOR ELECTRONS

The “*Programmable phase plates for electrons*” Interdisciplinary Training Webinar was recorded and webcast on 30 May 2018, during the first [International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#) at [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#). The conference was organised by Q-SORT and the “[Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#)” DIP project (*Deutsch-Israelische Projekt cooperation grant*) with the support of [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#) and the [Nanoscience Institute of CNR \(CNR-NANO\)](#).

The webinar featured one of conference invited speakers, **Prof. Johan Veerbeek (University of Antwerp, Belgium)**.

Webinar viewers reached 6.6K for the talk of Johan Veerbeek. Facebook posts related to the webinars held during the Conference reached over 60k people.

The webinar was recorded with one camera, then stored on remote servers for subsequent on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Johan Veerbeek (Antwerp University, Belgium) and Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED).

The webinar can be re-watched on demand - interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following link:

<https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/videos/1282830615183640/>

3.1 DESCRIPTION

The webinar touches upon the following topics:

- spatial light modulators
- coherent phased arrays
- vortex waves / vortex beams
- electrostatic and magnetostatic electron lenses
- programmable electron phase plates
- quantum coherence
- MEMS
- ptychography.

In light optics, spatial light modulators currently allow full control over the wavefront of optical waves, which has led to many new applications, ranging from astrophysics to advanced light microscopy. Analogous devices for electron optics approach the flexibility of spatial light modulators, yet still pose constraints due to the difficulty of exerting extended coherent control over the phase. In the webinar a new idea is illustrated which seeks to overcome some of these limitations.

The webinar was aimed at:

- spreading awareness amongst physicists of the new possibilities afforded by spatial light modulators
- exchanging ideas between scientists for furthering joint research
- promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities, establishing a common language between the two disciplines.

A lively Q&A session followed after the webinar.

Figure 1 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 3

Figure 2 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 3

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the third Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced for Q-SORT by [QED](#), with additional support from partner [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#).

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of the previous ones and use it as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium create, promote, and deliver even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: PROGRAMMABLE PHASE PLATES FOR ELECTRONS

Phase manipulation?

SLM: Spatial light modulator

In optics: freely programming phase is a reality

SLM based on mirrors

J. Bryzek, A. Flannery, D. Skurnik **Integrating microelectromechanical systems with integrated circuits** IEEE Instrum Meas Mag, 7 (2004), pp. 51-59

Yuanping Song, Robert M. Panas, Jonathan B. Hopkins, A review of micromirror arrays, Precision Engineering, Volume 51, 2018, Pages 729-761.

Applications SLM

- superresolution: structured illumination
- optical depth sectioning
- quantum encryption with a classical key
- self tuning microscope: adaptive optics
- vortex coronagraph
- particle manipulation
- tractor beams
- suppressing central beam in holography
- ...

Imaging through a multimode fiber

Fig. 1. Experimental setup for imaging through a multi-mode fiber (MMF). (a) In calibration, a $65\times$ objective lens and camera are placed at the MMF output to record intensity patterns generated there. (b) In imaging, an object is placed at the MMF output and illuminated by intensity patterns, and the reflected power coupled back into the MMF is recorded. The setup can use localized spots or random patterns at the MMF output for sampling the object.

Reza Nasiri, Mahalati, Ruo Yu Gu, Joseph M. Kahn, OPTICS EXPRESS 21-1 (2003)1656

Coherent phased array

Jie Sun, Erman Timurdogan, Ami Yaacobi, Ehsan Shah Hosseini & Michael R. Watts
Nature 493, 195–199 (10 January 2013) doi:10.1038/nature11727

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Can we do it also with electrons?

At 300kV, $v \sim 0.78c$, $\lambda = 2$ pm

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Circular aperture (normal STEM)

$$d_{50} = \lambda / \alpha$$

Diffraction limited probe

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Vortices in waves

Vortex waves (singular optics)

Size of a vortex beam

Figure 2: (a) Fourier space representation of a Bessel beam Ψ_1 (see eq. (1)). The radius of the ring is equal to the transverse momentum k_{\perp} . (b) Radial intensity for different topological charge. For $l = 0$ we obtain the well known Airy disc, for $l \neq 0$ doughnut like intensity distributions are obtained.

Verbeeck, Jo, Giulio Guzzinati, Laura Clark, Roeland Juchtmans, Ruben Van Boxem, He Tian, Armand Béche, Axel Lubk, and Gustaaf Van Tendeloo. 2014. "Shaping Electron Beams for the Generation of Innovative Measurements in the (S)TEM." IF2013=1.639. *Comptes Rendus Physique* 15 (2–3): 190–99. doi:10.1016/j.crhy.2013.09.014.

$$d_{50} = \sqrt{m+1} \lambda / \alpha$$

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Electron vortices

K.Y. Bliokh^{a, b, *}, I.P. Ivanov^c, G. Guzzinati^d, L. Clark^{d, e}, R. Van Boxem^d, A. Béché^d, R. Juchtmans^d, M.A. Alonso^f, P. Schattschneider^g, F. Nori^{a, h}, J. Verbeeck^d, Theory and applications of free-electron vortex states, Physics Reports 2017

Non diffractive beams

- Solution of 3D Helmholtz equation where wavepacket does not change upon propagation (propagation invariant optical fields)
- Requires solution to be decoupled in transverse and longitudinal part
- Cartesian (1D): plane wave
- Circular cylindrical (1D): Bessel beams
- Elliptical cylindrical (2D): Mathieu beams
- Parabolic cylindrical (2D): Parabolic nondiffracting beams, Airy beams

Peculiar non-diffracting beams

Make your own with: `wavepropagate.m`
[github.com/joverbee /some_matlab_codes](https://github.com/joverbee/some_matlab_codes)

Berry, M. V.; Balázs, Nándor L. (1979). "Nonspreading wave packets". *American Journal of Physics*. **47** (3): 264–267. [doi:10.1119/1.11855](https://doi.org/10.1119/1.11855).

Siviloglou, G. A.; Broky, J.; Dogariu, A.; Christodoulides, D. N. (2007). "Observation of Accelerating Airy Beams". *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **99** (21): 213901. [Bibcode:2007PhRvL..99u3901S. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.99.213901](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.99.213901).

J E Morris, T Čižmár, H I C Dalgarno, R F Marchington, F J Gunn-Moore, K Dholakia, *Journal of Optics* **12**, 12 (2010)

The toolset of an e-wave crafter

Different strategies

E field

- photons (Kapitza Dirac, ponderomotive force)
- atoms (weak phase objects)
- electrostatic lenses
- electrostatic mirrors
- RF fields (ponderomotive)

Magn. Vector potential

- photons
- magnetic atoms
- electromagnetic lenses
- electromagnetic mirrors
- RF fields

exception:
selectively block
electrons (holographic
reconstruction)

Tuning the phase of electrons

AB phase, either magnetic or electric

$$\Delta\Phi_{AB} = \frac{e}{\hbar} \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{A} \cdot d\mathbf{l}$$

$$\Delta\Phi_E = \frac{\pi}{\lambda E_0} \int_{\Gamma} eV(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{l}$$

Good news: control fields to control phase

Tool 1: Holographic reconstruction

Conventional electron holography

Optical reconstruction: recreates the Complex wave

All holograms
holo_reconstruction.m
<https://github.com/joverbee/som...>
Check it out and have fun!

Example: making a vortex beam

Hologr. reconstruction

Verbeeck, J. and Tian, H. and Schattschneider, P., 'Production and application of electron vortex beams', **Nature** 467(2010) 301-304

Realisation of vortex beams in TEM

Practical realisation of vortex beams in TEM!
Many applications exist for optical vortex beams

Verbeeck, J. and Tian, H. and Schattschneider, P., 'Production and application of electron vortex beams', **Nature** 467(2010) 301-304

Alternative setup: Spiral

N.R. Heckenberg, R. McDuff, C.P. Smith, A.G. White, Generation of optical phase singularities by computer-generated holograms, *Optics Letters* 17 (3) (1992) 221–223.

Verbeeck, J.; Tian, H. & Beche, A. 'A new way of producing electron vortex probes for STEM', *Ultramicroscopy* **113**, (2012) 83-87.

Holograms?

Lets make an aberration corrector!

- Can we use a neg Cs wave as desired wave?

Cs -1mm

Left beam is Cs
Central is uncor
Right beam is C

Cost=50\$ (factor 200.000 lower than real corrector)
Downside: unwanted beams, reduces intensity

Alternative with quadratic ref wave

Cs -1mm
-100,0,100nm defocus

Solved mostly the issue
with sidebands

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Tool 2: Aharonov Bohm effect

$$\varphi = \frac{q}{\hbar} \int_P \mathbf{A} \cdot d\mathbf{x},$$

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{q\Phi}{\hbar}.$$

THE PHYSICAL REVIEW

A journal of experimental and theoretical physics established by E. L. Nichols in 1893

SECOND SERIES, VOL. 115, No. 3

AUGUST 1, 1959

Significance of Electromagnetic Potentials in the Quantum Theory

Y. AHARONOV AND D. BOHM
H. H. Wills Physics Laboratory, University of Bristol, Bristol, England
 (Received May 28, 1959; revised manuscript received June 16, 1959)

In this paper, we discuss some interesting properties of the electromagnetic potentials in the quantum domain. We shall show that, contrary to the conclusions of classical mechanics, there exist effects of potentials on charged particles, even in the region where all the fields (and therefore the forces on the particles) vanish. We shall then discuss possible experiments to test these conclusions; and, finally, we shall suggest further possible developments in the interpretation of the potentials.

Purely QM effect, no forces involved

FIG. 2. Schematic experiment to demonstrate interference with time-independent vector potential.

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Example Cs/Cc corrector TEM

Haider-Rose-Urban legacy
Driving force behind nearly all
progress in TEM since the 1990-ies

resolution $\sim 20\lambda$

M. Haider et al. Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A 2009;367:3665-3682

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Airy wave

$$\Psi(x, z) = \text{Ai} \left(\frac{x}{x_0} - \frac{z^2}{4k^2 x_0^4} \right) \cdot \exp \left(i \left(\frac{xz}{2kx_0^3} \right) - i \left(\frac{z^3}{12k^3 x_0^6} \right) \right)$$

$$B_2 = 3A_2$$

$$\Phi_{31} = \Phi_{33} + \frac{\pi}{3}$$

G. Guzzinati, L. Clark, A. Bch, R. Juchtmans, R. Van Boxem, M. Mazilu, and J. Verbeeck, "Prospects for versatile phase manipulation in the TEM: Beyond aberration correction," *Ultramicroscopy*, vol. 151, 2015.

Using a magnetic monopole?

FIG. 43. Electron wave front incident on monopole.

A. Tonomura, Applications of electron holography. Rev. of Mod. Phys. 59, 639-669 (1987)

A. Béch, R. Van Boxem, G. Van Tendeloo, and J. Verbeeck, "Magnetic monopole field exposed by electrons," Nat. Phys., vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 26–29, Dec. 2013.

Aharonov Bohm phase shift

$$\varphi = \frac{q}{\hbar} \int_P \mathbf{A} \cdot d\mathbf{x},$$

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{q\Phi}{\hbar}.$$

$m = \pm 1$

requires a single
flux quantum
through the needle

$$\Phi = \pm \Phi_0 = \pm h/2e$$

saturation field 2T would require cross section of 1000 nm²,
 in fact we have 225x12 nm² active material

a flux quantum is not the smallest amount of flux

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Dynamic vortex creation

after a lot of tedious FIB work...

it flips!

High resolution using vortex beams

High resolution on STO, standard $\alpha=20$ mrad HAADF conditions (governed by source size broadening)

High resolution on $Mn_2Sb_2O_7$, $\alpha=8$ mrad HAADF conditions (governed by diffraction limit)

A.Béché, R.Juchtmans & J.Verbeeck, Ultramicroscopy (2016)

Pi beam with magnetic needle

Béché et al., *Nature Physics*, 10(1), 26–29 (2013)
Blackburn and Loudon, *Ultramicroscopy*, 136, 127–143 (2014)

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Mapping phase in plasmons?

G. Guzzinati, A. Béche, H. Lourenco-Martins, J. Martin, M. Kociak, and J. Verbeeck, "Probing the symmetry and phase of localised surface plasmon resonances with singular electron probes," Nature Communications 2017. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1608.07449>

Experiment

G. Guzzinati, A. Bch, H. Lourenco-Martins, J. Martin, M. Kociak, and J. Verbeeck, "Probing the symmetry and phase of localised surface plasmon resonances with singular electron probes," Nature Communications 2017. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1608.07449>

Tool 3: refractive optics, MIP

$$\Delta\phi = -\frac{qVt}{\hbar},$$

Electrostatic AB effect
V gets projected along
trajectory

$\text{Exp}(-i \text{cte } V) \sim 1 - i \text{cte } V + \dots$

Problems:

- phase contrast
- 2D projection

Weak phase
object

Projected potential

Final speed is same
But time delay depends
on how long you stayed
at higher potential

In fact the projected
potential in the direction
of motion

Remember:
True science and
skateboarding are
more closely related
than you would think

TEM Phase Plate examples

N. Frindt, PhD thesis, "Development and implementation of electrostatic Zach phase plates for phase contrast transmission electron microscopy", University of Heidelberg, 2013 (<http://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/archiv/14570>)

Phase plate based on MIP

R. Shiloh, Y. Lereah, Y. Lilach, and A. Arie (2014)
Sculpturing the electron wave function using
nanoscale phase masks, *Ultramicroscopy*. 144, 26–
31.

V. Grillo, G. Carlo Gazzadi, E. Karimi, E.
Mafakheri, R.W. Boyd, and S. Frabboni (2014)
Highly efficient electron vortex beams generated
by nanofabricated phase holograms, *Applied
Physics Letters*. 104, 043109

MIP based vortex mask

A. Bch, R. Winkler, H. Plank, F. Hofer & J. Verbeeck
Micron 80 (2016) 34–38

problems: thickness depends on HT, contamination, charging

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A refractive Cs corrector?

Figure S5: Optical microscope images of the window side of one window of (a) a commercial membrane with a 110 μm edge, and (b) our in-house-fabricated membranes with a 230 μm edge. Inset: flat side showing 9 open apertures of bare silicon nitride (blue) in the Au layer (yellow). Both are 200 nm silicon nitride, coated with Cr and Au from the window side, and show a milled 100 μm corrector. In (b), there is faint evidence of the 120 μm -diameter aperture on the flat side's Au layer. Varying colors result from different illumination conditions. The contrast and brightness have been changed for visibility. In (a), we did not have a Au layer on the flat side.

Roy Shiloh, Roei Remez, Peng-Han Lu, Lei Jin, Yossi Lereah, Amir H. Tavabi, Rafal E. Dunin-Borkowski, Ady Arie, Spherical aberration correction in a scanning transmission electron microscope using a sculpted thin film, *Ultramicroscopy*, Volume 189, 2018, Pages 46-53,

Fig. 4. Spherical aberration: (a) fabricated phase-mask, dashed line marking extents of the intensity cross-section in the inset. (b) Measurement and (c) focal series simulation. Contrast and brightness altered for visibility.

Shiloh, Roy, Roei Remez, and Ady Arie. 2016. "Prospects for Electron Beam Aberration Correction Using Sculpted Phase Masks." *Ultramicroscopy* 163. Elsevier: 69–74. doi:10.1016/j.ultramic.2016.02.002.

Figure 1: Schematic diagrams showing the setup for aberration correction using a foil corrector and experimental measurements. (a) An electron probe formed using a standard limiting aperture is ideally affected only by spherical aberration. (b) Equal but opposite spherical aberration is introduced by a foil corrector, yielding a spherical-aberration-free probe. The phase corrector comprises a membrane that has varying thickness along its radial direction, as indicated using a dotted black line. Without correction, Si <110> dumbbells cannot be resolved, either (c, e) in an HAADF-STEM image or (g) in its Fourier power spectrum. When using the corrector, 136 pm Si dumbbells are visible, both (d, f) in an HAADF-STEM image and (h) in its Fourier power spectrum. The images were denoised slightly (see raw data and details in the Supplementary Material). The black line profiles in (e, f) show the raw data averaged over the marked regions in (c) and (d), respectively. The scale bars in (c) and (d) are 500 pm.

Tool 4: Einzel lens

Figure 1. Scanning electron microscopy image of a Zach PP. The structure consists of a central electrode surrounded by an insulating layer (dark contrast) that is completely covered by a shielding metal layer. The PP tip is positioned in the vicinity of the undiffracted electron beam in the BFP of the objective lens.

Zach phase plate

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image of the Boersch phase plate. (b) Five-layer structure of the electrode ring.

Boersch phase plate

<http://simion.com/info/lens.html>

Majorovits, E., B. Barton, K. Schultheiß, F. Pérez-Willard, D. Gerthsen, and R. R. Schröder. 2007. "Optimizing Phase Contrast in Transmission Electron Microscopy with an Electrostatic (Boersch) Phase Plate."

Ultramicroscopy 107 (2–3): 213–26. doi:10.1016/j.ultramic.2006.07.006.

Schultheiss, Katrin, Joachim Zach, Bjoern Gamm, Manuel Dries, Nicole Frindt, Rasmus R Schröder, and Dagmar Gerthsen. 2010. "New Electrostatic Phase Plate for Phase-Contrast." *Microscopy & Microanalysis* 16 (6):

785–94. doi:10.1017/S1431927610093803.

A 2x2 programmable phase plate

J. Verbeeck, A. Bch, K. Mller-Caspary, G. Guzzinati, M. Anh Luong, M. Den Hertog, Ultramicroscopy **190**, 58–65 (2018) and <https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.11373>

Results

What about decoherence?

Weak coupling between wall
 in thermal equilibrium and
 quantum state of electron
 Coupling scales with length L
 And with distance $1/d^2$

S. Uhlemann, H. Müller, J. Zach, M. Haider, Thermal magnetic field noise: electron optics and decoherence, *Ultramicroscopy* 151 (2015) 199–210
 S. Uhlemann, H. Müller, P. Hartel, J. Zach, M. Haider, Thermal magnetic field noise limits resolution in transmission electron microscopy, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 111 (4) (2013),
 A. Howie, Addressing Coulomb's singularity, nanoparticle recoil and Johnson's noise, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 522 (2014) 12001.

Upscaling the design

- ERC Proof of Concept project ADAPTEM
- Target > 5x5 array
- How many pixel elements do we need?
- What configuration is best?
- How to address these pixels?
- What about fill-factor?
- Reliability?
- Manufacturability?
- How to place them in a microscope?

European
Research
Council

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Wouldn't it be nice?

Beam shaping experiments would become far easier and tunable

Useful as aberration corrector?

Possible use cases

- Dynamic ptychography
- Exotic beam shaping
- Aberration correction in TEM and SEM
- Coherence control (randomized phase)
- Contrast enhancement (e.g. plasmon symmetry, gradient of phase, edge enhancement)
- In sample focusing
- Iterative Phase measurement (e.g. LowPhi method?)

Optical depth sectioning

What you want

Using time reversal we see that in principle a wave exists that focuses perfectly on a single atom

Iterative optimisation of wave to improve localisation of wanted signal

Routinely used in e.g. Leica optical microscopes

What you get

Reducing beam broadening

Optimised probe: reverse multislice

Radially averaged optimized

Tool 5: ponderomotive force

- Path of electron in oscillating optical field becomes also a meandering path
- The average forward speed of the electron doesn't change
- But the path length is now long as the trajectory was meandering
- This depends on the amplitude of meandering and is proportional to E^2
- Assumes a gradual entry and exit of optical field (so that average field remains zero)
- Does not depend on direction of E field (polarisation)
- Does not require a standing wave per se
- Force relates to gradient of this phase
- Electrons are expelled from intense photon field regions
- This is an elastic effect (energy of electron is preserved after leaving the field, at least on average)

trajectory

$$\mathbf{F}_p = -\frac{e^2}{4m\omega^2} \nabla(E^2)$$

$$V_{pond} = \frac{eE^2}{4m\omega^2}$$

$$\Delta\phi = -e^2 \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E|^2 dz}{4m\omega^2 v \hbar}$$

Use same way as MIP (but no material)

Simulation of e-path through Gaussian laser beam of 100W with 1um beam waist. Amplitude ~ 7pm

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Kapitza Dirac

Jonathan Handali, Pratistha Shakya, and Brett Barwick,
"Creating electron vortex beams with light," *Opt. Express*
23, 5236-5243 (2015)

10^{11} W/cm^2

P. L. Kapitza and P. A. M. Dirac, "The reflection of electrons from standing light waves," *Proc. Camb. Philos. Soc.* 29 (02), 297–300 (1933).

Tool 6: mirrors?

compensate bad lenses with equally bad mirror

target for 5eV
 LEEM 2λ
 =1 nm

R.M. Tromp, J.B. Hannon, A.W. Ellis, W. Wan, A. Berghaus, O. Schaff
 Ultramicroscopy 110 (2010) 852

Conclusion

- Proof of concept SLM for TEM exists
- Upscaling is in progress
- Expect to see more when MEMS chips are ready (IMC Sydney?)
- Decoherence can be kept reasonable
- Theorists...we need simulations with this newly gained degree of freedom

Acknowledgements

- Martien den Hertog, CEA Grenoble
- ERC POC

- We are hiring: Come join us in this development
- <https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/rg/emat/organisation/open-positions/>

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL